

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF CONTACTS BETWEEN THE PROsthESIS BASE AND THE PROstHETIC BED

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Abstract

Treatment of patients with complete absence of teeth involves the use of various methods and materials. Their objective assessment requires determining the percentage of contact between the base of the manufactured prosthesis and the prosthetic bed. Clinical practice also needs to evaluate between the base of a new prosthesis and the prosthetic bed. To achieve this, the use of objective assessment methods is necessary. For any successful prosthetic restoration, the accuracy of the fit of the prosthesis to the prosthetic bed is critical.

Keywords: Complete removable denture, contact between the denture and the denture bed, indicator paste.

One of the methods for finding and eliminating inconsistencies is the use of indicator pastes (PI) for the correction of dentures. According to GPT: PI is any substance used in dentures that shows how they adapt and adhere to opposing structures [3]. Typically, PIs are used for problems associated with [7]:

1. Excessive pressure.
2. Excessive expansion of the boundaries of the prosthesis.
3. The gap between the prosthesis and the prosthetic bed.

Good relationship and fit of the prosthesis are especially important, since the criterion for functional suitability is the value reflecting the distance between the mucous membrane and the prosthetic surface. In an environment where there is no access to air, the force required to separate two adhered surfaces is inversely proportional to the distance between them [1].

The purpose of the study is to propose a method for assessing contacts between the base of complete dentures and the denture bed using PI for the correction of dentures.

Material and methods.

To assess the contact between the base of the new prosthesis and the prosthetic bed, we settled on the Hydent PI, in the form of a spray containing zinc oxide and isobutane as a propellant. PI was sprayed directly onto the prosthetic base from a suitable distance. Spraying is not difficult, but if you do not have the necessary experience, the paste may start to spread, excessive material may accumulate, or bubbles may appear in certain areas. Like classic, creamy PIs and sprays, it is possible to shape the furrows with a brush. After applying the PI to the prosthetic, you can spray the surface with an insulating silicone spray. Research shows that after using a silicone aerosol, a clearer pattern is obtained, and the danger of the material sticking to the mucous membrane is significantly reduced. In the absence of an isolator, Kenneth Shay et al. (2010) suggest dipping the prosthesis with the indicator paste already applied into

a cup of cold water before inserting it into the oral cavity [4]. Before installing a prosthesis in the oral cavity, the following rules must be observed [6]. If the mucous membrane is thin and atrophic, the prosthesis is carefully installed in the oral cavity, then the dentist applies light palpation pressure on the first molars. If the mucous membrane is pliable, the dentist places cotton swabs in the area of 6 teeth and the patient applies strong compression to them. Occlusal contacts should not be allowed, as this can lead to displacement of the prosthesis and changes in pressure distribution. If there are premature contacts, then the observed pressure areas will be erroneous.

The occlusion is checked and corrected after the fitting of the prosthetic base is completed. Only then can a final check of the base fit be carried out, in which pressure is applied by the teeth in central occlusion. To decipher the results of using the indicator paste on the prosthesis, 3 areas were examined. Results. According to Stevenson-Moore et al. (1979), the load on the prosthesis is distributed unevenly throughout the prosthetic bed. When force is applied, the load falls on isolated areas between the base and the mucosa. It has been established that no less than 40% and no more than 85% of the total area of the prosthetic bed is in contact with the prosthetic base. Firtell et al. (1985) show that most potential hot spots occur when using zinc oxide indicators rather than silicone indicators. For both types of indicators, observed potential areas of excessive pressure detected on the day of delivery of the prosthesis are more common than those actually recorded at the follow-up examination 24 hours later [2]. It is for this reason that areas with excessive pressure are corrected only if there is irritation of the mucous membrane. It is logical to expect stronger pressure on the immobile mucous membrane, which does not need correction if there are no complaints from the patient.

Conclusion.

The practical results of the described method give us reason to conclude that there is not 100% contact between the new complete denture and the prosthetic bed. The described method can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of new materials and treatment methods for patients with complete dentures.

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